
Bank Runs: A Review of Literature

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Abstract

Banks are important economic growth agents globally because of their roles in the intermediation of funds for investment and entrepreneurial activities. There is a relationship that develops between parties in the process of intermediation; the Banker-Customer relationship. The contract in the banker-customer relationship requires the bank to pay the customers whenever withdrawal requests are made, failure in this regard can lead to panic and a bank run. Bank runs occur when a large number of customers request to withdraw their deposits simultaneously. Bank runs can occur out of rumor or genuine reason of illiquidity in specific financial institutions. This study is motivated to contribute to the discussions on the multi-dimensional causes of Bank Runs and the impact of this occurrence on the banking industry and the economy. This descriptive study looks into the extent to which bank runs are driven by genuine concerns about bank liquidity and stability rather than rumor or panic about the failure of another bank within the financial system. It was discovered that households 'Propensity to Run' increased when they received negative news about the illiquidity or collapse of a banking institution. The study recommends strengthening the supervision roles of Regulatory Authorities.

Keywords: *Bank Runs, Intermediation, Propensity to Run, Money Deposit Banks (MDBs), Corporate Governance, Deposit Insurance Scheme*

JEF Codes: *G21, G28, E58*

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INTRODUCTION

Financial institutions play a fundamental role in the growth of any economy. Banks are an important part of the financial systems. Savings and investment processes are organized around banks as financial intermediaries in every economy, making banking an important part of the economic growth process (Ifeanyi et al., 2024). Banks take savings and deposits from the surplus sector of the economy and lend to individuals and corporate entities in the shortage sector of the economy. Financial intermediation is, therefore, a major function of the banking sector in the economy. In the process of intermediation, Banks enter into relationships with their customers. This Banker-Customer relationship places some responsibilities on the banker and the customer. The banker is expected to pay customers, on demand, the deposits by these customers. It is, however, assumed that all depositors will not demand payment of their deposits simultaneously. The banker, therefore, strikes a balance by ensuring adequate liquidity to satisfy withdrawals considering the Central Bank's Monetary Policy Ratios. Bank's inability to satisfy customers' withdrawal requests could be interpreted as illiquidity by the customers and may lead to a bank run. Bank Runs is a situation where customers of a bank, in large numbers, request to withdraw their deposits at the same time, almost always, out of panic that the bank is experiencing liquidity challenges and that it may soon run out of cash (Cookson et al., 2023). The most commonly used definition of a bank run is the occurrence of multiple, virtually simultaneous deposit withdrawals, whether successful or not (Barth et al., 2023). Bank runs are not all of a kind, they can be divided into two different types: Fundamental bank runs and Contagious bank runs. A fundamental bank run arises when there is the withdrawal of deposits because a bank cannot meet its contractual obligations, whereas a contagious bank run takes place when depositors' perception of a bank's fundamentals suddenly changes e.g., due to the publicity of negative information that is not directly relevant to their financial position, such as liquidity or solvency (Sandri et al., 2023). Depositors, in this case, withdraw funds because they are worried by the existence of rational fears rather than because they may be fundamentally distressed. The fact that we distinguish between these two types of bank runs is important because the sustainability of a bank in a world with these features may be drastically different.

The word 'run' often connotes a scenario where depositors scramble to withdraw some or all of their funds from a shaky or insolvent bank. More generally, runs are also taking place in banking systems where many banks may be solvent to begin with but consequently fail because of a purely self-fulfilling prophecy (Altermatt et al., 2024). Bank runs have caused

great distress and consumed financial wealth in many countries throughout recorded history. Their huge social costs have pushed bank runs to the center of studies at most banking and policy discussions. This essay explores two aspects of bank runs: their causes and consequences. This study is, therefore, motivated to contribute to discussions on the multi-dimensional causes of the phenomenon and the impact on the financial industry of any country. Though there is a limited number of literature on this phenomenon locally, there is quite a sizeable documentation on bank runs from the international scene.

This study is, therefore, aimed at a detailed review of the concept of Bank Runs and identifies the causes and implications of this phenomenon on shareholders, employees, the financial industry, the regulatory authorities, and the economy. The study will also identify the various strategies the regulatory authorities employ to ensure Bank Runs do not happen or the occurrence reduced to the barest minimum. The following questions will also be addressed in this research; what triggers the need for depositors, in large numbers, to want to withdraw all or some of their deposits from a bank? Can a run on a bank cause another bank in the region to experience continuous and rapid withdrawal of deposits by its customers? Could false information in social media cause a bank to experience a run even when such information is not specifically on the bank? Could crises within the Board and Management of a financial institution lead to a run on the institution? Whether a run can lead to a bank failure.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Bank runs represent some of the most unique dynamics of financial markets. A bank run has acquired some old connotations, with an increased demonstration in any current occurrence over the past ones. Traditionally, bank runs are characterized by withdrawals in cash or bank deposits made out of fear or informational aversion to bank futures (Abidi et al., 2024; Borneman, 2023). Various factors could contribute to the reason how a bank would reach the state of not being able to uphold its responsibility of meeting the withdrawal requests of its depositors. The common perception of a bank run is that it is a self-inflicted crisis; depositors rush to get their assets, fearing that the bank will run out of cash and close. Only then does the bank fail, leaving some depositors empty-handed. (Sandri et al., 2023). This view of a bank run as an idiosyncratic event has led some economists to suggest that these events are not of inherent concern because the costs are confined to the liquidation of the failing bank and the loss of the particular set of depositors that ran. Of course, if depositors'

runs can trigger debt runs, then bank failures would impose large costs on depositors who did not run. If the failed bank is large or connected enough, some runs can snowball into a systemic event furthering economic contraction.

Bank runs are evidence of bank distress that might lead to bank failure, collapse, or liquidation. A bank is distressed when it can not meet its customers' withdrawal requests (Ogege, 2021). Bank distress could happen due to several factors;

Micro-Economic Factors;

- Capital inadequacy
- Poor Management of the Bank/Management Crisis
- Weak Internal Control Systems
- Poor Risk Management Systems
- Related party Credit
- Fraud
- Board Crisis

Macro-Economic Factors;

- Non-compliance with regulatory standards
 1. Monetary policy ratios
 2. Liquidity ratio
 3. Cash reserve ratio
 4. Deposit/loan ratio
- Frequent changes in economic policies
- Poor of Corporate Governance
- Technological innovation & Fintech fraud

In the context of banks, distress can be transmitted from one firm to another. This system risk is commonly referred to as Contagious Bank runs and it happens during general panic or economic downturns. These banks, because they are connected or "too big to fail," impose costs on the entire economy when they fail (Berndt et al., 2024; Abidi et al., 2024). There are several historical examples to suggest that a set of individual bank runs in a panic can lead to systemic failure across an economy. This suggests that bankers and regulators should be vigilant for the early signs of bank distress and do what they can to prevent them from spreading. In principle, the safe and concurrently least distortionary way to accomplish this is with adequate capital requirements for all financial institutions.

THEORETICAL REVIEW

There is a plethora of theories that dwell on the liquidity of financial institutions. These theories include Financial Intermediation Theory, Commercial Loan Theory, Shift Ability Theory, Liability and Liquidity Management Theory, and Liquidity Preference Theory. This study will be based on the Theory of Financial Intermediation introduced by Merton & Bodie, (1995) in their Conceptual Framework for analyzing financial systems. This theory focused on the mediatory service performed by banks in linking economic agents with surplus funds and economic units with deficit funds. This is critical in capital formation for real investment and in the reduction of informational asymmetries. The process of intermediation provides banks with the capacity to mobilize deposits and provide credit for individuals and entrepreneurs for investment activities. The traditional model of bank intermediation could be traced to the 18th-century classical economics works of Adam Smith, which postulates that banks create money from deposits (Efuntade & Efuntade, 2023). The economists assumed that depositors do not withdraw their deposits or savings simultaneously and that banks only need to hold a fraction of the total deposit to meet the withdrawal requests of the customers. The banker would thereafter, be able to create large quantities of deposits through credits or loans. The services provided by financial intermediaries are essential for investment and economic development (Gbadebo, 2024). To ensure continuous economic growth, the Apex Bank provides a supervisory role of ensuring that the financial system within the country is strong and stable (Azolibe, 2022). Banks account for a significant proportion of financial system assets within the country, therefore, a well-controlled and stable financial system increases investors' confidence in an economy. The Central Bank, as a banker to the banks and lender of last resort, provides financial backup for banks to ensure that banks do not just fail where there are adequate liquid assets to prevent failure (Wachukwu et al., 2023).

EMPIRICAL REVIEW

Empirical evidence on bank runs shows that it is a common phenomenon in the financial systems of various countries, and this is further documented as case studies. Bank failure is, therefore, not restricted to developing or underdeveloped economies, but it is a global phenomenon. The factors leading to bank runs are often related to the strength, or lack thereof, of regulations and efficient management of resources.

Limodio & Strabbe (2023), in their study on liquidity requirement, bank deposits, and financial development, confirmed that customers are encouraged to deposit money with the

bank when the bank's liquidity or stability is evident. This implies that there is increased confidence in the capacity to pay whenever there is a withdrawal request. Banke & Yitayaw (2022), further enthused that the safety of the bank and the security of the banking system encourage deposits from customers. Benov & Simenova (2021), however, agreed that rumors and unfavourable news about a financial institution might provoke panic withdrawal of deposits and lead to severe bank runs. Kiss et al., (2022), argued that liquidity shocks in a bank can result in panic withdrawals and runs that may ultimately lead to bank failure. Sandri et al., (2023), also concluded that poor corporate governance issues in a bank could easily lead to panic withdrawal of deposits and bank runs. Panic withdrawal of deposits from a bank can trigger a contagious effect on other banks within the region where depositors are aware of any financial connectivity between the institutions (Marodin et al., 2024). A cordial relationship between a bank and its customers tends to reduce the negative perception of customers about the fragility of any banking institution (Warren, 2024). Ashar et al., (2024), however, revealed that uninsured depositors are most likely to engage in panic withdrawal of deposits.

Toby & Danjuma, (2021) and Bala-Keffi, (2022), used exploratory research design to review the issue of liquidity management and capital structures of banks in Nigeria and the inefficient allocation of resources. The use of short-term funds to finance long-term assets is a familiar practice by Nigerian banks. It is a common sight to see the acquisition of huge head office buildings and other long-term assets by Nigerian banks only for them to struggle under liquidity pressures, this is the bane of several failed banking institutions in the country. Between 1986 and 1998, 31 banks were liquidated in Nigeria for various reasons but notably for illiquidity, poor asset quality, weak corporate governance, and gross insider abuse (Ughulu & Odion, 2023). Oladeji, (2022), reviewed the impact of the Central Bank's monetary policy pronouncements such as Cash Reserve Ratio (CRR), and Lending ratio, on the level of liquidity in banks and concluded that, while a high CRR limits banks' ability to create money, it helps banks to withstand and survive the pressure from panic withdrawals and severe runs. Bateman, (2022), considered the impact of rumors and unfounded information about the liquidity status of a banking institution on the possibility of runs on a bank. The study concludes that misinformation in social media could not only cause but exacerbate runs on a bank, particularly from uninsured depositors (Fong, 2021). Martins, (2023) agreed on the possibility of runs on another bank in the same region where the saving public has the impression that a strong financial relationship exists with a bank currently experiencing runs.

This contagious situation resulted in the collapse of several banks in Nigeria in the 90s (Olawale, 2024).

METHODOLOGY:

This study employed a descriptive research methodology and utilized secondary data that have already been validated and used in published works. These data were sourced to enable a well-articulated review of the causes and consequences of Bank Runs. An extensive review of available local literature and works on international scenarios was conducted to be able to answer the research questions and show the impact of this phenomenon on the stakeholders and the economy at large.

GENERAL DISCUSSION:

Crises in banking are a global occurrence that happens from a combination of factors that may be exogenous or endogenous. Damiano et al., (2023), focused on the collapse of Silicon Valley Bank (SVB) and the perspectives of households on bank stability. The authors also delved into the potential for panic-driven bank runs and the role of public communication. Panic was the primary cause of bank failure during the great depression of the 1930s (Monnet & Ungaro, 2021). The authors pried into the extent to which bank runs are driven by genuine concern about bank liquidity and stability rather than panic or rumor as a result of the failure of another financial institution. Households react differently to news of bank illiquidity and the risk of bank failure. People's propensity to withdraw money from ailing banks "Propensity to Run" is different based on how long they have banked with the banking institution showing the relevance of the banker-customer relationship. Worried about deposit safety, households could be prompted to withdraw more money, but would rather increase precautionary savings rather than increased consumption. No household would withdraw money because of worries about bank liquidity and spend such funds on buying a car or using such money for a family vacation. Households would rather hold more liquid cash to protect the family from unusually long periods of instability in the financial institution.

Liu & He (2022) on their part, focused their study on the hypothesis of asymmetric information, where the literature features models in which bank runs are due to customers' perceptions of the stability of the financial institution. Banks hold relatively illiquid and long-term assets, while claims on the banks are short-term in nature. Furthermore, information

about the quality of assets, held by banks, is very important and relevant to the perception of the savings public.

PUBLIC COMMUNICATION AND BANK RUNS

Media coverage and reporting of happenings in the banking industry are important as misinformation could wreak havoc on an industry important to the economy. Household expectations of a banking institution based on rumors and unfounded information may spread rapidly though incorrect. A rumor is an unverified account or explanation of events circulating from person to person (Varshney & Vishwakarma, 2021). The notion of a rumor is interesting because the underlying mechanism of information transmission is often considered person-to-person. Rumor-aided bank runs are a difficult situation for bankers because of the panics that always accompany such situations and always make it essentially difficult to extinguish. In a world in which new technologies accentuate the ease at which information is spread at an alarming rate through social media, the control of disinformation as it relates to any financial institution is fairly more difficult to mitigate. Weird messages spread and contagious to the rest of the banking sector could be only a click away. It is most important to show that – if a crisis occurs – sociologists have argued that such a crisis can be seen as a liquidity event, characterized by coordination problems and rapid expectations adjustments (Flores & Gross, 2022). A bank run in an interconnected system is no longer a phenomenon governed by rationality theory but by a belief that a bank will not be able to satisfy your withdrawal request (Challoumis, 2024). We are now in the paradox of living in a world where we understand that information has to spread to maintain stability. But too much information can also create panic. This is the social dilemma and intricacy of the modern-day banking system where the coordinated duty of the mass media has to be harmonized with the need for spreading information. Murmurs and runs can become a self-fulfilling prophecy (Ifeanyi et al., 2024), in other words, it could result in a bank failure. The cornerstone of the banking business has always been fair disclosure. Publishing as much information as you can is essential in a crisis. But diffusing the wrong message to the mass public is also a tragedy. If the information is bad, you could create a panic even for a sound bank. So, one facet of the problem becomes: how to deal with the information that is spreading so rapidly? In other words, if information is costly, while it should ideally be consumed, it is the case of not over-consuming. If such information in a world is relevant and counterproductive to spread rapidly, we are again looking at the ancestors of who should coordinate this diabolic action. This may point to how

critical and relevant the central bank is, the authority that ensures that no such information travels to halt the smooth functioning of the banking system and the growth of the economy. However, how much information is too much should, essentially, be contextual and bank-specific (Martins, 2023).

PSYCHOLOGICAL AND BEHAVIOURAL ASPECT OF BANK RUNS

The basic question of why depositors get worried and start withdrawing their funds has not been satisfactorily answered and for many decades was at the heart of the academic debate on bank runs. There are some empirical reasons given by the new view of bank runs that can be used to begin answering this question. For instance, a correspondence analysis of bank-run data from the 1970s concludes that individual depositors draw conclusions about the solvency of their bank based on the withdrawals of informed depositors and further that only the amounts of informed withdrawals mattered to the majority of depositors (Dietrich et al.2024). This account demonstrates the existence of two important aspects of any run process: the presence of a behavioral reaction and the emergence of further withdrawals based on this behavior. Fear and panic are emotional factors and important determinants of withdrawal behavior (Fletcher & Aunger, 2024). For instance, the report of a bank run is known instantly and may evoke feelings of panic, engendering a critical reevaluation of decisions. As a consequence, depositors might behave accordingly, independently of the risk parameters of the bank they are dealing with. Once a depositor's decision has some range of alternatives that he cannot drive every possible equilibrium according to the standard recipe of equilibrium selection in games with multiple solutions, there is room for him to display hope, despair, and trust. This appears to indicate that any explanation of bank runs should include some psychological and behavioral factors (Zhao et al., 2022). Indeed, deeming depositors 'irrational' in one sense or another is a long-standing tradition in the field. Most times, however, the action of those who decide to run is based on factors that are not that 'irrational' in the real sense —though the result is 'irrational'.

BANK RUNS AND FINANCIAL STABILITY

It is unclear how much damage stemmed from bank runs in the past because bank runs engulfed broader banking systems and precipitated financial instability, rather than setting off isolated problems. A framework with liquidity frictions shows that a broken financial system precipitated by bank runs adversely affects the real economy in terms of output, investment,

and unemployment as firms face uncertainty, difficulties in accessing credit, and uncertainty in getting paid. (Michail, 2021; Noth and Schüwer, 2023). Since bank runs spread across financial intermediaries, it is critical to monitor the financial health of all entities in desired banking systems, as well as risks stemming from interactions among interconnected intermediaries such as hedge funds and insurance companies. The "Lender of Last Resort" can be there to serve as a "firefighter," but the institution cannot employ a "preventive" stance. (Bohoslavsky et al., 2022). Bank stability is relatively easy to demonstrate. Banks can prevent bank runs with liquidity and capital buffers, as depositors can easily enforce adverse selection punishment by withdrawing deposits if they believe banks are becoming insolvent. To the extent that continuation in this equilibrium hinges on deposits and lending practices, a bank needs to engage in conservative banking activities, i.e., "not make bad loans." By matching assets with liabilities in this arena, the bank can protect itself from failure (Guzel, 2021). The anatomy of bank runs and the causes of bank panics garnered more attention early in the 20th century. A model infers that depositors cannot distinguish which information is good and which is worthless. The cause of interaction creates a self-fulfilling prophecy causing bank insolvencies. If a bank's equity capital falls below its deposit base due to waves of withdrawals, a bank run occurs. A bank cannot attach a future return on assets to shareholders and debt holders, and individually withdrawing funds allows a depositor to make a successful gamble that the distress bank will fail.

CONCLUSION, POLICY IMPLICATIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Regulators should think about ways of making banks and the financial systems in which they are embedded more robust if bank runs occur. This requires focusing attention on the commitments of governments to deposit insurance and liquidity management commitments. This is vital because, as things stand today, the threats from both liquidity shortages and rumors have magnified effects on deposit values and lending behavior, leading to bank runs. Banks should think about ways to credibly communicate to incoming depositors that one run, or even a rumor of a run, will not start future spirals of withdrawal and bank sales; i.e., the commitment of the government to implement liquidity management commitments should be strengthened. Regulatory authorities should provide continuing policy communications on the stability of the banking system as this would go a long way to reducing the Propensity to Run by depositors during rumors. Governmental intervention should be based on the premise that

the market process and failing of the market require a stabilizing third party such as a government regulatory agency.

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